

Recommended citation: Isaac, S. (2020). Leveraging Epistemic Practices to Scaffold Engineering Students' Thinking From Paper-Based Exercises to Open-Ended Projects. In van der Veen, J., van Hattum-Janssen, N., Järvinen, H.-M., de Laet, T., & ten Dam, I. (Eds.), *Engaging Engineering Education. SEFI 48th Annual Conference* (pp. 223-231). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Enschede, The Netherlands. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14653752.

SCAFFOLDED STEPS TO DEVELOPING ENGINEERING STUDENTS' EPISTEMIC THINKING FROM PAPER-BASED EXERCISES TO OPEN-ENDED PROJECTS

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Conference Key Areas: *Future engineering skills, Challenge based education*

Keywords: *epistemic beliefs; problem solving; authentic learning; engineering skills*

ABSTRACT

While professional engineers must frequently make compromises between competing outcomes and take decisions in the face of uncertain information, multiple studies have identified that most engineering students are ill-equipped to confront such situations. These skills fall into the category of sophisticated epistemic practices, an area of engineering students' training which is persistently underdeveloped.

The fine-grained approach of Elby & Hammer's relatively recent epistemic resources model takes a practical approach to observing the ways in which students interact and manipulate knowledge. This study exploits their approach to confirm the relevance and generalisability of Gainsburg's 2015 characterisation of the use of mathematical models in engineering. It uses an *a priori* analysis of the think-aloud problem solving behaviour of 8 engineering students in Switzerland.

An important outcome of this engineering-specific, fine-grained approach is that it can be implemented by teachers following Finster's recommendation that teachers design activities that challenge students to use $n+1$ strategies in order to promote the development of epistemic thinking. Consideration of the epistemic nature of these small strategies can assist teachers to create scaffolded steps for learners to acquire the sophisticated knowledge practices required to address real-world, complex problems both as students and graduates.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Why epistemic sophistication matters for engineering students

The increasingly complex and trans-disciplinary nature of professional engineering practice requires a well-developed understanding of the nature of knowledge². The importance of epistemic sophistication for engineers is ubiquitous in the literature, in order that students “will be more capable of addressing engineering problem-solving in real world contexts because of their ability to see problems from multiple perspectives and recognize that more than one right answer exists” [1]. More prosaically, epistemic sophistication is present in the accreditation of engineering programs; for example 4 of the 11 student outcomes required by ABET explicitly include the complex context of environmental, social and ethical constraints [2]. The persistence of naïve conceptions in engineering graduates is clearly problematic. For example, a graduate with an unexamined trust in figures of authority and a belief in the existence of a single correct answer to real world applied engineering problems is ill-suited to exercise the judgement required of a certified engineer. It is thus disconcerting to note that Pavelich & Moore [3] and Wise *et al.* [1] found only a quarter of engineering students who completed their undergraduate degrees held sufficiently sophisticated epistemic beliefs to choose appropriately between competing knowledge claims in a complex environment.

Although the study of epistemic beliefs has attracted significant research effort since its inception in 1970 by William Perry, a model that permits robust quantitative measurement has proved elusive. This study takes a pragmatic approach to epistemic beliefs by focusing on students’ epistemic practices [4], which are the sense-making and knowledge justification strategies, employed during problem solving. This characterisation of engineering students’ more and less sophisticated epistemic practices is desirable as it can serve to assess students’ ability to confidently navigate in complex, open-ended engineering environments.

1.2 A succinct literature review

There is near-unanimous agreement that naïve epistemic beliefs take a dualist, absolutist view of knowledge, while a more sophisticated epistemic approach involves an awareness of the constructed and evolving nature of knowledge and the development of criteria against which to evaluate knowledge claims. However neither the early stage-based models nor the semi-independent dimensions models have an adequate empirical foundation [see 4]. The long-running debate about the generalisability of epistemic beliefs has been decided in favour of domain-specificity. However, taking “science” as a discipline is clearly too broad, as illustrated by Tsai’s study showing differences in students’ epistemic conceptions in physics and biology [5].

² This area was historically referred to as ‘personal epistemology’ but is now plagued with a chaotic mess of terminology. Please see [4].

Elby and Hammer's cognitive resource model [6-7] marks a significant departure from previous models by taking a highly contextualised, fine-grained approach to characterising the different ways that students interact with knowledge. Their model seeks to address two major shortfalls of previous models; (1) instruments that are too general and coarse-grained, and (2) a failure to differentiate between the correctness and productivity of different epistemic practices. Elby and Hammer's model posits that people have a set of cognitive resources from which they chose which element to bring to bear in each specific context. The naïve approach will be the most effective, and thus appropriate, in some situations despite the range of strategies available to the student. In fact, rapidly alternating between high and low epistemic approaches resembles the problem solving of expert engineers, as the applied nature of engineering involves repeated navigation between abstract models and physical reality. For Elby and Hammer, effective epistemic cognition is adopting an appropriate knowledge practice for a specific knowledge claim. Thus, higher epistemic sophistication is not identified by the consistent use of high-level behaviours but rather an ability to select and employ productive cognitive resources.

Gainsburg's 2015 study [8] investigated, in the fine-grained manner of Elby and Hammer, the problem solving behaviours of 9 American civil engineering students' while working on their homework assignments. She identified various behaviours representative of the use of mathematical models in engineering problem solving and then organised them into a 4-level framework of increasing epistemic sophistication.

The current study has 2 aims. First, to test the relevance of Gainsburg's model in a novel culture (Switzerland) and across multiple study programs, and secondly, to leverage these observations to examine how the learning tasks can be structured to better support students' epistemic development.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Think-aloud problem solving protocols

Think-aloud protocols were used to provide information about the strategies and approaches used by students during problem solving. While this method requires students to verbalize their thought processes, a task constrained both by cognitive load limits and the self-awareness of the student, it makes the connection between epistemic conceptions and actions visible. The think-aloud problem solving protocol was immediately followed by a stimulated recall interview which focused on elements relevant to epistemic beliefs. Each student's own written work was used to structure and anchor the interview.

2.2 Problem solving tasks to elicit epistemic practices

A series of 4 tasks were designed to require a diverse set of problem solving strategies without requiring knowledge beyond that of a typical first year engineering curriculum. While the think-aloud tasks were intentionally constructed to avoid providing any formulae or equations, the problem statements were designed to

prompt students to remember and use fundamental equations from physics and thermodynamics. Each task was presented in a contextualised format to offer opportunities for students to verify the plausibility of answers or to employ real life observations. An example was the possibility to use whether a 10 degree temperature change would be acceptable for an *in situ* dental polymerization as advance problem solving.

2.3 Analysis Using Gainsburg’s Model as a Framework

Gainsburg’s descriptions of epistemic practices [8: p.156] were culled to those relevant to an isolated think-aloud problem solving task. This meant eliminating behaviours which would not occur outside the context of a course, such as “Sees no connections among course content (unless topics are identical).” The behaviours retained are presented in *Table 1* and were used as *a priori* codes to mark specific episodes in the transcripts across both the problem solving and stimulated recall portions of the interviews. This short study does not make a distinction between enacted behaviours, such as a student previewing her method for how to go about solving the problem, and professed beliefs, such as recounting her habit of discussing different problem solving approaches with other students. Sessions with students lasted between 60 and 90 minutes, largely depending on students’ facility and determination in solving the exercises. In total, the data comprised 79 coded episodes, with 8 to 14 episodes per student.

Table 1. Selected Codes for Engineering Students’ Enacted Epistemic Views [8]

Stage 1 – Dualism	Stage 2 – Integrating	Stage 3 – Relativism	Stage 4 – Sceptical reverence
Believes engineering can be done as a purely mathematical enterprise	Will step back and look at the overall picture	Seeks deep understanding even if it delays solving the current problem	Big picture present throughout problem solving
Goal for exercises is to get the right answer	Goal for exercises is to train the mind	Verify solution using own experiences	
Answer key or instructor sole means of verifying solution	Uses units on intermediate values to guide solving process	Attempts to relate values to physical phenomena, to guide solving	Assess reasonableness of answers, computer output
No effort to connect mathematical procedures to real-world phenomena	Sense-making using concepts, math	Sense-making using real world observations	Recognises fallibility of models, need to understand underlying assumptions
Little trust that peers have useful ideas about problem solutions	Discusses with peer to refine understanding	Discusses with peer to learn from peers’ ideas about	Recognises non-routine nature of solving problems and the need for judgement

		solving methods, even if imperfect	
Pattern-matches to previous problems, without understanding	Uses methods other than those of instructor	Previews task and states overall plan and predicts result	

2.4 Participants

Following approval from the institutional human research ethics committee, eight students from a range of different study programs were recruited. Purposeful sampling was employed to obtain diversity in the year of study and study program, as presented in *Table 2*. Students are identified by a pseudonym of their own choosing, where a name beginning with A indicates a first year student and a first letter C name is a third year student.

Table 2. Study participants

Pseudo	Year	Study Program
Amandine	First	Computer engineering
Anna	First	Electrical engineering
Antoine	First	Life Science engineering
Benoît	Second	Microengineering
Boris	Second	Mechanical engineering
Clément	Third	Microengineering
Damien	Master1	Technology Entrepreneurship (B.Eng electrical)
Ernest	Master2	Environmental engineering (B.Eng civil)

3 RESULTS

3.1 Epistemic behaviours exhibited by students during problem solving

Applying the behaviours described by Gainsburg, listed in *Table 1*, as *a priori* codes allowed the frequency of behaviours at each level to be recorded. It is important to note that the observed behaviours are diverse in nature, ranging from a single instance constructing a table of values, *as he always does with this kind of exercise*, despite not being sure what is asked (level 1) to reporting that the solutions provided by the instructor would be the only way to check a calculated answer (level 1). Further, the number of codes per level is not consistent. It is thus simplistic to report the level which occurs most frequently as though each behaviour is of equal importance, but it does provide a crude measure of the range and distribution of students' various epistemic practices.

Despite the relatively brief format of the sessions, each student was observed to use a range of different approaches, as shown in *Table 3*. All students exhibited at least one example of level 1 behaviour and at least one example of level 3 behaviour, with

the exception of Benoît. Benoît did not exhibit any level 1 behaviour and was unique to demonstrate awareness of the limitations of the models underlying the equations employed during the problem solving (level 4). The most common level 1 behaviours were making no attempt to relate mathematical procedures to real-world phenomena and seeing the goal of exercises as getting the right answer. Using concepts and maths to make sense of the tasks, illustrated by Anna's quote below, were by far the most common level 2 behaviours. Sense-making using real world observations was the most common level 3 behaviour, illustrated by Ernest's quote below.

« When air condenses to solid on the windshield... logically, when it freezes it would lose energy, right? Yeah, because it changes state. The vibrational state is lower. » Anna

"I was thinking more like on the street, like I'm walking in the winter. It's winter, therefore it is cold. I just don't picture myself taking energy from another object. It's just me losing the energy." Ernest

"Given that chemists invented the mole, which is very practical, it not surprising that they use it in concentration. This is not an equation where I have a lot of doubt. However, there is more ambiguity in the equation I used a minute ago, $PV=nRT$. There are a lot more hypotheses behind it. Here you can't be in just any conditions, it is more complicated, there are approximations." Benoît

Table 3. Frequency of Behaviours Exhibited by Students in Think-aloud & Interview

Name	1 – Dualism	2 – Integrating	3 – Relativism	4 – Sceptical reverence
Amandine	2	4	2	
Anna	1	6	4	
Antoine	2	5	1	
Benoît		7	3	1
Boris	4	5	1	
Clément	5	6	3	
Damien	2	5	1	
Ernest	2	6	1	

All students were observed to use level 2 most frequently, despite all students exhibiting higher level behaviour on at least one occasion. This broad range and below-peak functioning is consistent with Gainsburg's study. A notable difference is that she found level 1 to be most commonly exhibited by students, but her participants were working on their own course work and had access to their notes. The tasks constructed for this study were intentionally unfamiliar to students and no study resources were provided, which makes many level 1 behaviours such as

pattern-matching less accessible. These differences are particularly salient given the context-dependant nature of the epistemic resource model employed in the study and serves to reinforce the findings. The differences between the observations of the two studies are interesting for what they reveal about how tasks can be designed to encourage students to use more sophisticated epistemic practices.

3.2 Implications for epistemic beliefs models in engineering

This study tested the generalisability of Gainsburg's model of epistemic beliefs [8] in engineering by asking students from several different study programs to solve think-aloud chemistry tasks with real world contextualisation. While some of the behaviours identified by Gainsburg were not observable in the experimental conditions of this study, most of the behaviours related to different problem solving approaches in levels 1, 2 and 3 were observed in this small study. As with Gainsburg's own study, level 4 behaviours were rarely observed. Thus, the observations of this study supports the relevance of Gainsburg's model across engineering disciplines and to non-Anglophone educational systems. Future work will include a grounded theory approach to the themes arising from the think-aloud data.

Observations in this study also support the epistemic resources model of Elby and Hammer [6-7], where individuals draw on the different resources available to them depending on what will be effective in the current context. Students were observed to employ a broad range of behaviours on the different tasks and at different moments during the tasks. Students were observed to function at level 2 most frequently, as this appeared to be most effective for the tasks at hand. This is consistent with Elby and Hammer's definition of epistemic sophistication as the ability to select and employ productive cognitive resources.

3.3 Recommendations for teaching engineering

Worryingly, students reported that the tasks and assignments which constitute the bulk of their university experience do not encourage them to adopt more sophisticated epistemic practices. Demonstrations of problem-solving and assigned exercises appear to nearly exclusively feature single, precise answer tasks that preclude the need to check the assumptions of the models used or tolerate uncertainty. The ability to calculate a highly precise answer was generally taken by students as equivalent to a highly accurate answer, completely ignoring any simplifications or approximations employed in obtaining the equation used to model the system. Further, it seems that assigned tasks rarely provide sufficient contextualisation for students to leverage their lived experiences for sense-making or answer checking, and do not require students to make estimates or work with imprecise values. These observations may contribute to why engineering students develop more slowly in their epistemic practices than other students [10].

In order to assist students in adopting more epistemically sophisticated practices, Finster [11] recommends that teachers create opportunities for students to employ n+1 strategies. The detailed, engineering-specific practices outlined in Table 1 can

serve as a guide for teachers to create appropriate n+1 activities that stimulate epistemic growth. Providing opportunities for students to work in less constrained, more imprecise situations, will better equip students to work on big, open-ended projects at school and in their future professional lives [1].

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This small study supports the 4 level framework of engineering-specific epistemic practices proposed by Gainsburg [8] and its generalisability to other areas of engineering. Additionally, the diversity and sub-peak behaviour functioning are coherent with the cognitive resource model of Elby and Hammer [6-7].

While Marra et al. [9] found that epistemic beliefs do change over 4 years of engineering undergraduate studies, Paulsen and Wells [10] found that, when controlling for other demographic factors, engineering students were more likely to hold beliefs about knowledge being simple and certain than other fields. This researcher hopes that the fine-grained characterisation of more and less sophisticated epistemic practices in engineering will make it more accessible for instructors to obtain insight into this aspect of engineering students' thinking and thus make targeting the development of such abilities a more explicit goal of their teaching.

I would like to thank Professor Paul Ashwin, Department of Educational Research, University of Lancaster, for useful discussions.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. C. Wise, S. H. Lee, T. Litzinger, R. M. Marra, and B. Palmer, 'A report on a four-year longitudinal study of intellectual development of engineering undergraduates', *J. Adult Dev.*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 103–110, 2004, doi: 10.1023/B:JADE.0000024543.83578.59.
- [2] ABET. Student Outcomes - Criterion 3 of Criteria for Accrediting Engineering Programs. 2018-2020 Accreditation Cycle. <http://www.abet.org/>
- [3] M. J. Pavelich and W. S. Moore, 'Measuring the effect of experiential education using the Perry model', *J. Eng. Educ.*, vol. 85, no. 4, pp. 287–292, 1996.
- [4] W. A. Sandoval, J. A. Greene, and I. Bråaten, 'Understanding and promoting thinking about knowledge: Origins, issues, and future directions of research on epistemic cognition', *Rev. Res. Educ.*, vol. 40, no. 1, pp. 457–496, 2016.
- [5] C.-C. Tsai, 'Biological Knowledge is More Tentative than Physics Knowledge: Taiwan High School Adolescents' views about the Nature of Biology and Physics', *Adolescence*, vol. 41, no. 164, 2006.
- [6] A. Elby and D. Hammer, 'On the substance of a sophisticated epistemology', *Sci. Educ.*, vol. 85, no. 5, pp. 554–567, 2001, doi: 10.1002/sce.1023.

- [7] D. Hammer and A. Elby, 'Tapping epistemological resources for learning physics', *J. Learn. Sci.*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 53–90, 2003, doi: 10.1207/s15327809jls1201_3.
- [8] J. Gainsburg, 'Engineering Students' Epistemological Views on Mathematical Methods in Engineering', *J. Eng. Educ.*, vol. 104, no. 2, pp. 139–166, 2015, doi: 10.1002/jee.20073.
- [9] R. M. Marra, B. Palmer, and T. A. Litzinger, 'The effects of a first-year engineering design course on student intellectual development as measured by the Perry scheme', *J. Eng. Educ.-Wash.-*, vol. 89, no. 1, pp. 39–46, 2000.
- [10] M. B. Paulsen and C. T. Wells, 'Domain Differences in the Epistemological Beliefs of College Students', *Res. High. Educ.*, vol. 39, no. 4, pp. 365–384, août 1998, doi: 10.1023/A:1018785219220.
- [11] D. C. Finster, 'Developmental instruction: Part II. Application of the Perry model to general chemistry', *J. Chem. Educ.*, vol. 68, no. 9, p. 752, 1991.